

HOW TO IMPROVE COMMUNICATION SKILL IN THE CLASSROOM

Zubaydullayeva Zarina Erkinovna

Tashkent Academic Lyceum 2 of the Ministry of
Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10432227>

Annotation: This article provides information about Developing classroom communication is vital to help children learn. And your communication skills can help you develop an ideal learning environment in several ways. We've outlined just a few of them here.

Key words: communication, building relationship, collaboration.

Great teachers know education is a two-way street. You can't treat children like empty vessels waiting to be filled with knowledge. They need to buy into the lesson. They need to be challenged. They need to discuss ideas. Promotes Learning

Your classroom should be noisy (at the correct times). Because children need opportunities to discuss ideas. Children internalise concepts and ideas more easily after talking them through. More confident pupils can also help guide less confident learners through tricky problems, developing both children's understanding.

How to Communicate Effectively in the Classroom

1) Build Relationships

As mentioned, children don't learn from teachers they don't like. Particularly vulnerable children who might've struggled at school in the past. They likely already have a negative view of school and those cruel adults who keep them there for six hours daily. If you've got pupils like this, you must build a relationship.

Take opportunities to talk to the child about non-school related things. Ask about hobbies, interests – anything that the child enjoys. And make sure you're ready at the start of every lesson to cheerily greet children as they enter the classroom. Let every child know you're happy to see them. And do this every day, no matter what happened in the last lesson. And this strategy isn't just for more challenging pupils. Every child will benefit from a kind greeting or a little one-on-one time with their teacher. Build up goodwill with every child; gradually, you should see a change in how they respond to you and your instructions.

2) Develop Routines

Every second counts in the classroom. And there are predictable things you'll say and do every day (stop talking and focus on your work, line up for assembly,

etc.), so why waste those extra moments repeating the whole phrase or every step of the instruction? Take some time early in the school year to establish clear expectations and routines. Explain to children exactly what you want in plain language, then slowly take words away. After some time, you could get what used to be a multi-step instruction down to one or two terms. For example, let's go back to lining up for assembly. Say to a class of children, "Line up;" after about 10 minutes of squabbling, you'll probably be left with a clump of children in the shape of anything other than a line. So start by breaking down your instructions – make it clear where the line should start, end and the order you want. After practising a few times, shorten your words until, eventually, you can command a neat, efficient queue to form with one utterance of the word 'line.'

3) Talk Less

This isn't about the economy of language like in the previous example. This strategy is all about giving children opportunities to talk. As a general rule of thumb, it's recommended children should talk more than you. John Hattie, lauded educational researcher, recommends this approach. Consider making these tactics commonplace in your classroom:

- Give children a moment to think after you've posed a question
- Don't just repeat and correct something a child says if it's wrong – allow them to reflect on and improve what they've said
- Use think, pair, share – ask a question and then let children discuss answers or ideas with their talk partners before sharing with the class
- Promote genuine class discussions – don't just go back and forth between you and the class; encourage other pupils to jump in and challenge or build on what children have said

4) Promote Collaboration

Think, pair and share is just one example of positive collaboration in the classroom. Promoting teamwork and on-topic talking amongst children has been shown to help children learn. It can be implemented in the classroom at no extra cost. Think about your seating plan and try and find good combinations of pupils that will work well together. But make sure you mix up the arrangements from time to time so all children get opportunities to work together. This helps children develop their own communication skills and helps promote collaboration among everyone. You can also consider peer tutoring. Place more confident learners with those who might be a little behind and you'll often find they start making progress. Just be sure that the less confident learners aren't

just copying. And also give the more confident children regular opportunities to work with pupils at a similar level.

5) Offer Immediate Feedback

Feedback is critical for children to make progress. And the sooner it's delivered, the better. People often have an image of teachers working late into the night, ploughing through a stack of exercise books to mark. And this is absolutely accurate (sorry). But you must work just as hard during lesson time too. Make sure you're moving around the room constantly, scanning for the children who haven't quite got it yet. A quick verbal intervention is more impactful than a whole page of written feedback delivered days after the task. These verbal interventions are also easier to deliver in a collaborative classroom. While children are talking together, you should listen to their conversations to check their understanding.

Used literatures:

1. Sword, R. (2020). Effective communication in the classroom: Skills for teachers.
2. НАЙИТОВА, У. (2021). SOME STROKES TO THE POEM OF THE SHODMONKUL SALOM. THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука, (10), 1033-1036.
3. Аликулова, М. (2023). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ЭПИТЕТОВ В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯХ АИ КУПРИНА. Scientific progress, 4(5), 387-390.
4. Teshabayevna, K. U. (2023). Some Aspects of Teaching the Russian Language in the Primary School. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 2(6), 43-45.
5. Курбанова, У. (2023). РАЗВИТИЕ ЛОГИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ МАТЕМАТИКЕ В НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССАХ. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 3(4), 565-569.
6. Isakovna, I. R. (2023). LITERARI THE ROLE OF IMAGE ENHANCEMENT TECHNIQUES IN THE PROGRESS. International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 3(07), 48-52.
7. Jurraevich, Y. J. (2022). COURSE OF EPILEPSY IN CHILDREN, PROGNOSIS AND REHABILITATION ISSUES. BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMYIY JURNALI, 2(11), 32-37.
8. Jurraevich, Y. J. (2023). Clinical Course of Epilepsy in Children, Prognosis and Rehabilitation Issues. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION, 3(6), 130-133.

9. Mukhtarova, H. K., & Istamov, M. B. (2022). Forensic Psychiatric Aspects of Patients Who Complete Socially Dangerous Actions. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HEALTH SYSTEMS AND MEDICAL SCIENCES*, 1(6), 28-31.
10. Мухторова, Х. К. (2023). КЛИНИЧЕСКИЙ СЛУЧАЙ ПАРАНОИДНОЙ ШИЗОФРЕНИИ НА НАЧАЛЬНОМ ЭТАПЕ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ БРЕДОВОГО ВАРИАНТА СИНДРОМА КАНДИНСКОГО-КЛЕРАМБО. *BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(11), 25-28.
11. Zakirovich, G. B. (2023). THE MAIN FEATURES OF KINESTHETIC STYLE IN LEARNING PROCESS. *Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*, 11(5), 61-69.
12. Gafurov, B. Z. (2023). ADVERTISEMENT TEXT AS A WAY OF INFLUENCE ON THE AUDIENCE. *Academia Science Repository*, 4(5), 443-448.
13. Gafurov, B. Z. (2023). REFLECTION OF STYLISTICALLY MARKED VOCABULARY IN ADVERTISEMENT TEXTS. *Horizon: Journal of Humanity and Artificial Intelligence*, 2(5), 425-428.
14. Zakirovich, G. B. (2023). ACCURACY AND FLUENCY IN LANGUAGE TEACHING. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 12(05), 19-25.
15. Zakirovich, G. B. (2022). Discourse about the peculiarities of the theme of male gender in advertising texts in Russian and Uzbek (on the material of medical vocabulary). *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 2(2), 4-8.
16. Камолова, К. Г. (2014). Проблема использования исторического опыта религий при воспитании личности. *Инновации в науке*, (33), 130-133.
17. Камолова, К. Г. (2021). АХЛОҚИЙ КАТЕГОРИЯЛАРНИНГ ИНСОН ҲАЁТИДАГИ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(11), 110-115.
18. Камолова, К. Г. (2017). Творческое применение религиозного опыта при воспитании верующих людей. *Актуальные вопросы общественных наук: социология, политология, философия, история*, (1-2 (61)), 63-67.
19. Tursunboev, B. (2022). Zamonaviy ingliz media diskursida " musulmon olami" tushunchasi tahlili. *Qar Du xabarlari*.
20. Norbutayevich, T. B., & Abdukhililovich, K. I. (2019). CHARACTERISTIC FEATURES OF NOUN PHRASES IN MODERN ENGLISH. *Вестник Науки и Творчества*, (2 (38)), 47-49.

21. Tursunboev, B. (2022). REPRESENTATION OF THE CONCEPT " MUSLIM WORLD" IN A MODERN ENGLISH MEDIADISCOURSE. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 2(5), 461-467.
22. Gulzira, B., Aybek, B., & Aysuliu, O. (2021). The Use of Lexical Units of Turkic Languages in German. *Academicia Globe*, 2(6), 241-244.
23. Gulzira, B., Aysuliu, O., & Aybek, B. (2021). Some difficulties of teaching speaking a foreign language. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(6), 510-516.
24. Normurotovna, I. G. (2022). THE SPIRITUAL-PHILOSOPHICAL LEGACY OF IBN SINA AS PER NEWLY ESTABLISHED FINDINGS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES* ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(5), 143-147.
25. Иззатуллаева, Г. Н. (2022, November). АБУ АЛИ ИБН СИНО АСАРЛАРИДА ФАЛСАФИЙ ҚАРАШЛАР ТАЛҚИНИ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION"* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 53-63).
26. Izzatullayeva, G. N. (2023). ABU ALI IBN SINO TA'LIMOTINING FALSAFIY QARASHLAR TAHLILI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(14), 756-759.
27. Хамроев, С. Б. (2023). Особенности Течения Шизофрении В Зависимости От Когнитивных Нарушений. *AMALIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(4), 190-193.
28. Bakoyevich, H. S. (2023). Improving the Diagnosis of Cognitive Disorders in Schizophrenia, Therapy Issues. *AMALIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(12), 373-380.
29. Bakoyevich, H. S. (2023, September). UNDERSTANDING OF THE DIAGNOSIS OF COGNITIVE DISORDERS IN SCHIZOPHRENIA. In " *ONLINE-CONFERENCE*" PLATFORM (pp. 359-360).
30. Khamroev, S. B. (2023). Characteristics of Cognitive Impairment in Schizophrenia. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(4), 61-70.
31. Andleeb, S. (2020). Communication barriers perceived by English language learners at university level in District Vehari. M.Phil Thesis, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur.
32. Mustapha, G. H. & Argungu, I. A. (2019). Importance of language in teaching and communication. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 3(8): 513-515.

